

SURFACE PRETREATMENT OF POLYMER COMPOSITES BY EXCIMER LASER FOR ADHESION BONDING

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the results of using a high power excimer laser (KrF, 248nm) to treat the jointing surfaces of glass fibre reinforced Liquid Crystal Polymer composites with the aim to remove surface contaminants and to increase roughness for adhesive bonding. Two joint patterns, lap-joint and butt-joint have been investigated. Results showed that surface-treatment by excimer laser with optimum processing parameters could etch away the polymer matrix and left the fibres undamaged. This surface morphology led to high quality adhesion bonding.

Keywords: Excimer laser, Surface treatment, Glass fibre LCP, Polymer composites, Adhesion bonding

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced polymer composites are being increasingly used in a wide variety of engineering applications such as automobile and aircraft components, body panels and structures. Joining of polymer composites during fabrication is always a challenging process for researchers. Established joining techniques used for metallic materials such as mechanical fastening can reduce the strength of the composites because the required holes may cause stress concentration and delamination. The preferred joining technique for many composite materials is adhesive bonding. Proper surface treatment of an adherend is one of the decisive factors for achieving high quality joint. Various surface treatments are practised but most of them have their own limitations i.e. solvent absorption by the matrix, mechanical damage to the fibre or degradation of the matrix [1-3]. Excimer laser, with its UV radiation energy similar to C-C bonds binding energy, can remove the organic contaminants such as fluorocarbons and silicones on the surface or ablate the polymer matrix and cause minimal fiber damage [3,4]. It was reported that surface treatment by excimer laser is an effective mean for improving adhesive bonding of polymer and its composites [3,5]. This paper will discuss the effects of KrF excimer laser surface treatment on lap- and butt-joint strength of fiberglass/LCP(Liquid Crystal Polymer) composite material.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS AND JOINT GEOMETRY

The polymer composite studied was a glass fibre reinforced liquid crystal copolyester (GF/LCP) with 30% weight fraction of glass fibres, (Vectra A130, supplied by Hoechst Co.). The composite was injection-moulded into slabs of dimension 150mm x 75mm. Specimen strips of dimension 74mm x 22.5mm x 1.2mm were cut off from the moulded slabs. The adhesive used was a two part epoxy resin (Araldite by Ciba-Geigy).

Both lap-joint and butt-joint were investigated. For the lap-joint, an overlap area of 22.5mm x 12.5mm were lap-joined at the short edges of the strips. The joined sample length was 135.5mm. A bondline thickness was controlled to be 100 μ m. For the butt joint, because of the moulded slab thickness was only 1.2mm, a butt joint of this dimension would introduce large experimental error. In view of this, five specimens were stacked together to make up a total thickness of 6.5mm. The butt joint cross-sectional area for each bunch of specimens was therefore 20mm x 6.5mm with a joined sample length of 70mm.

The joint strengths were determined by tensile tests using Instron Model 4301 at a cross-head speed of 2mm/min and 23°C. For each set of conditions, three to five tests were carried out. The laser-treated and fracture surfaces were examined by SEM.

JOINT SURFACE TREATMENT

A KrF excimer laser was used to treat the jointing area of the specimen surfaces. The maximum output energy of the laser at 248nm radiation is 800mJ per pulse. The specimen was placed on a NC X-Y table under a stationary beam which was focused by quartz compound lenses. The energy intensity on the specimen surface was controlled by the output energy and the defocussed beam size on the specimen surface. The specimen was scanned at a table speed 'v' mm/sec. A metal mask with a square slot of (a) mm x (a) mm was placed in the laser path just above the specimen and ensured a constant irradiated area. The equivalent number of pulses, N, at any position of the irradiated region was calculated as follows:

$$N = f(a/v)$$

where f is laser pulse repetition rate in Hz.

For comparing purposes, some specimens were subjected to abrasive cleaning or chemical cleaning prior to adhesive joining.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

SELECTIVE ABLATION OF THE COMPOSITE

With the optimised processing parameters, the excimer laser beam can selectively etch the constituent phases of a polymer composite. Fig 1 is a typical example that at a suitable energy intensity, it was possible to ablate the LCP matrix effectively without affecting the glass fibres. Fig 1a-d show the surface morphologies of the irradiated region after treated by different number of pulses at 10 Hz and 173mJ/cm². It is obvious that the amount of matrix removed depends upon the total number of pulses. Fig 1a shows that the glass fibres being locked by the matrix effectively. As the number of laser pulses were increased, the glass fibres gradually "surfaced"

Fig.1 SEM photographs of the fibreglass/LCP composite treated by KrF excimer laser with energy density of 173mJ/cm² at replate of 10Hz. (a) untreated (b) 10 pulses (c) 50 pulses (d) 200 pulses.

Fig.2 SEM photographs of the fibreglass/LCP composite treated by KrF excimer laser with energy of 393mJ/cm² at replate of 10Hz. (a) (b) 50 pulses (c) (d) 200 pulses.

out. This indicated that the extent of matrix being removed can be precisely controlled by laser etching. It is also important to note that the glass fibres were unaffected by the number of pulses as long as the energy intensity was below a critical value, as shown in Fig 1d.

However, if the energy intensity was above a certain threshold level, damage to the glass fibre could be catastrophic. Fig 2a-d show that at an energy intensity of $393\text{mJ}/\text{cm}^2$, the glass fibres were seriously damaged. As the chemical bonds in the inorganic glass cannot be ablated by the 248nm radiation, the laser energy is absorbed and accumulated in the form of heat. When the heat accumulation gradually increased, it was enough to soften the glass fibres. This is shown in Fig 2d in which the glass fibres were in a curly form as compared with the straight fibres in Fig 1d. The damage mechanism and phenomenon on the glass fibres as shown in Fig 2a does not seem to be the result of pure thermal effect and more investigation is needed for clarification.

In contrast to the glass, the organic polymer absorbs UV radiation energy which is in the same range of their molecular bond binding energies and results in photoablation and bond rupture. As the long polymer molecules are fragmented suddenly, the low molecular species are released at a high rate and results in a sudden expansion in volume. The low molecular species which are in gaseous form are being explosively ejected away from the parent material.

STRENGTHS OF THE LAP-JOINTS

The lap-joint strengths of GF/LCP composites treated with different surface treatment techniques are shown in Fig 3. It is obvious that the excimer laser surface treatment is most effective in obtaining a strong lap-joint. The lap-joint strength of the laser treated samples is 33% higher than that of the untreated ones, and also higher than that of the abraded or acetone cleaned ones.

Figure 4 shows the fracture surfaces of the lap-joints. For the specimen in which no surface treatment had been applied, fracture occurred at the bonding interface and the surface layer of the adherends. For the acetone cleaned specimen, fracture occurred mainly at the surface layer of the adherends. Thus, besides the contaminated or low energy surface, the existence of a weak sub-surface layer in the composite also contributes to the low lap-joint strength. After laser treated or Silicon Carbide paper abrasion, both the surface contaminants and the weak subsurface layer were removed. This enables a better quality adhesion bond to be achieved and fracture in fact occurred inside the adherends. This fracture mode also suggests that the lap-joint strength of this glass fibre reinforced LCP composites is difficult to be enhanced further. This is mainly due to that the orientation and the layered structure of the fibres and LCP are in the same injection direction of this single gated injection moulded slab.

Fig. 3 Lap-joint strengths for fibreglass/LCP composite

Fig.4 Fractural surface morphologies of lap-jointed fibreglass/LCP composites.

STRENGTHS OF THE BUTT-JOINTS

Fig 5 shows the micrographs of the laser treated edges of the composite. The edge is perpendicular to the injection flow direction. It can be seen that the LCP matrix had been removed but the fibres left behind dangling. As shown in Fig 6, this edge treatment is surprisingly effective on improving the butt-joint strengths. The butt-joint strength of the laser treated specimen is about one time higher than those of the untreated one and the mechanically abraded one. Furthermore, the extent of improvement in the butt-joint strength is also dependent on the number of laser pulses on the edges.

Fig.5 SEM photographs of the edges treated by the excimer laser

Fig.6 Butt-joint strengths for the surface treated composite

CONCLUSION

Excimer laser is a very useful tool to treat the surfaces of polymer composites for achieving high quality adhesive bonds. In addition to the ability to remove surface contaminants and change the chemical activity of a polymer surface, excimer laser can selectively ablate the polymer matrix and leave the fibres undamaged as long as the energy intensity is below a critical value. Surface pretreatment by excimer laser is very effective in improving the adhesion bonding, specially, butt-joint of fibreglass/LCP composite. This suggests an interesting industrial application of excimer lasers.

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